

A multidisciplinary approach to engineering

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Editorial

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On behalf of the entire Editorial Board, I am very pleased to announce the launch of a new journal called the Multidisciplinary Journal of Engineering Sciences. As the name suggests, it is a journal associating works in the broadly understood field of engineering. In today's world, advancements related to technology and engineering play a significant role in the lives of people around the world. Engineering data is becoming more complex, covering ever-larger areas of related disciplines and an ever-expanding time span. When considering a single, but very important part of engineering sciences, namely the environmental area, we can see that data solving the multidisciplinary problems confronting today's engineering researchers involves the knowledge to use available data and information to make their decisions [1]. Engineering issues that will be considered in the publishing process in the discussed journal include in particular such areas as chemistry and physics, which are the basis of engineering research. Therefore, already at the stage of education in the field of engineering, the curriculum should include issues related to chemistry [2]. It is similar to the field of physics, physics courses are among the main subjects for mechanical and electrical engineering students [3]. Therefore, conducting research in this area and publishing their results openly to everyone is extremely important nowadays. Advanced research on materials has seen the development of issues from the macro to the nanoscale. The creation of technology using nanomaterials is one of the greatest technical achievements that took place at the end of the 20 century. Currently conducted research is more and more advanced and developed. It is expected that scientific and technological progress in the current century will be very much determined by the achievements related to nanomaterials and their application in various domains of scientific and engineering studies [4]. Nanoscale is currently being used, for example, in a form of carbon-based nanomaterials where it has gained considerable importance for a number of usages. Their excellent physicochemical characteristics have prompted intensive research to assess their capability as gas sensing materials [5]. In turn, issues related to carbon will be an important part of the energy, environmental

protection, and mining related to the extraction and exploitation of coal, and thus the release of significant carbon dioxide emissions. Coming back to the materials issue, in the last couple of decades, high-tech polymeric materials have become more common in developing environmentally friendly uses for the agricultural sector. Intelligent polymer solutions have made a huge contribution to the agro-industry by increasing the productivity of fertilizers, as well as pesticides and herbicides. [6]. Bioengineering is an important element in broadly understood engineering, as it is connected with agriculture and industry systems, which are valid subject of this journal. The digital intelligence industry is the frontline industry of social progress these days. Among other things, it plays a role in economic development and is also exposed to global competitive pressures [7]. Hence, this journal could not be complete without issues related to new information and electronic technologies and on existing problems in the development of electrical engineering. Another thematic group covering engineering issues in a related way includes engineering management, which concentrates on integrating scientific, engineering and management issues to successfully and effectively make a contribution to the operation of industry, society and organizations [8]. Current social and technological changes pose new challenges to researchers following the latest scientific discoveries. Commitment to the development of knowledge needed to design more

efficient socio-technical systems is particularly important from an engineering point of view. The scope of this type of research includes industrial engineering and production processes, management engineering, and technological processes. This discipline brings together management, taking into account the technical nature of the managed processes, which makes up engineering management. The last of the important parts falling within the scope of the journal is the construction, operation, and modification of processes and technological products.

Types of articles, objectives, and scope

The new open-access journal, established under the title of Multidisciplinary Journal of Engineering Sciences, is an international peer-reviewed open-access journal, which allows readers to access the content of the articles free of charge, and consider for publication articles covering all the areas described above. We highly encourage academic authors from around the world to publish research results in this journal. All articles undergo a thorough review process to ensure the highest quality of published content for readers.

Conflict of interest:

The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

- Gibert, K.; Horsburgh, J. S.; Athanasiadis, I. N.; Holmes, G. Environmental Data Science. Environmental Modelling & Software 2018, 106, 4–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.04.005>.
- Altarawneh, M.; Dlugogorski, B. Z. Introducing Quantum Chemistry in Chemical Engineering Curriculum. Journal of Chemical Education 2018, 95 (9), 1562–1571. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.8b00422>.
- Z. Hari, A. Anuar, M. Z. Mokhtar and R. Mokhtar, "Evaluating engineering students performance in physics courses during foundation studies," 2016 IEEE 8th International Conference on Engineering Education (ICEED), Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 2016, pp. 214–217, doi: 10.1109/ICEED.2016.7856074.
- Guz, A.N., Rushchitskii, Y.Y. Nanomaterials: on the Mechanics of Nanomaterials. International Applied Mechanics 39, 1271–1293 (2003). <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:INAM.0000015598.53063.26>
- Hejazi, M.-A.; Eksik, O.; Taşdelen-Yücedağ, Ç.; Ünlü, C.; Trabzon, L. Carbon-Based Nanomaterials in Gas Sensing Applications. Emergent Materials 2023, 6 (1), 45–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42247-023-00454-7>.
- Sikder, A.; Pearce, A. K.; Parkinson, S. J.; Napier, R.; O'Reilly, R. K. Recent Trends in Advanced Polymer Materials in Agriculture Related Applications. ACS Applied Polymer Materials 2021, 3 (3), 1203–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsapm.0c00982>.
- Wu, G. Study on New Technology of Electronic and Information Engineering. In PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2015 INTERNATIONAL INDUSTRIAL INFORMATICS AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING CONFERENCE; Yang, L., Zhao, M., Eds.; ATLANTIS PRESS: 29 AVENUE LAVMIERE, PARIS, 75019, FRANCE, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.2991/iicec-15.2015.152>
- Elia, G.; Margherita, A.; Passiante, G. Management Engineering: A New Perspective on the Integration of Engineering and Management Knowledge. IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management 2021, 68 (3), 881–893. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tem.2020.2992911>.